

GOUT AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH GOUTY NEPHROPATHY: AN ANALYSIS OF 46 PATIENTS

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Introduction: Gout is a metabolic disease characterized by the accumulation of uric acid in the body, leading to the formation of crystals. Gouty nephropathy, as a complication of gout, refers to kidney dysfunction in patients suffering from this condition. This thesis explores the biochemical markers associated with gout and gouty nephropathy, particularly focusing on the role of creatinine and uric acid levels in the development of the disease.

Data: 1. Patients: 46 patients diagnosed with gout, including 3 females and 44 males.

2. Age Range: Patients are aged between 40 and 70 years.

3. Gouty Nephropathy: 20 male patients were diagnosed with gouty nephropathy, with 15 of them being older than 50.

4. Biochemical Analysis Results: Creatinine Levels: 20 patients had creatinine levels above 130 mmol/l (normal creatinine levels for men are 62-106 mmol/l, and for women, 53-97 mmol/l).

Uric Acid Levels: All patients had elevated uric acid levels, confirming the diagnosis of gout.

Older Patients (Above 50 years): Among those over 50 years old, creatinine levels were higher, exceeding 130 mmol/l, and uric acid levels were above 7 mg/dl (normal uric acid levels for men are 3.5-7.2 mg/dl, and for women, 2.6-6.0 mg/dl).

Analysis: Creatinine Levels: Elevated creatinine levels indicate impaired kidney function. The higher creatinine levels in patients over 50 suggest a greater risk of developing gouty nephropathy. Monitoring creatinine is crucial in assessing kidney damage in gout patients.

Uric Acid Levels: Elevated uric acid is characteristic of gout and is linked to the formation of uric acid crystals in the kidneys and joints. The higher levels of uric acid in patients over 50 indicate a more severe progression of gout and an increased risk of nephropathy.

Clinical Implications: The correlation between age and biochemical markers shows that gout and its complications, such as gouty nephropathy, are

more prevalent in older individuals, and these patients require careful monitoring and management.

Conclusion: Elevated creatinine and uric acid levels are significant biochemical markers in the diagnosis and progression of gout and gouty nephropathy. Patients over the age of 50 are at higher risk of developing kidney complications, making it essential to monitor these markers regularly and initiate early treatment to prevent further damage.